

Systematic review

1. * Review title.

Give the title of the review in English

Diagnostic methods of root caries lesions, a systematic review

2. Original language title.

For reviews in languages other than English, give the title in the original language. This will be displayed with the English language title.

Métodos de diagnóstico de lesiones de caries radicular, una revisión sistemática de la literatura

3. * Anticipated or actual start date.

Give the date the systematic review started or is expected to start.

14/09/2020

4. * Anticipated completion date.

Give the date by which the review is expected to be completed.

23/12/2020

5. * Stage of review at time of this submission.

Tick the boxes to show which review tasks have been started and which have been completed. Update this field each time any amendments are made to a published record.

Reviews that have started data extraction (at the time of initial submission) are not eligible for inclusion in PROSPERO. If there is later evidence that incorrect status and/or completion date has been supplied, the published PROSPERO record will be marked as retracted.

This field uses answers to initial screening questions. It cannot be edited until after registration.

The review has not yet started: No

Review stage	Started	Completed
Preliminary searches	Yes	Yes
Piloting of the study selection process	Yes	Yes
Formal screening of search results against eligibility criteria	Yes	Yes
Data extraction	No	No
Risk of bias (quality) assessment	No	No
Data analysis	No	No

Provide any other relevant information about the stage of the review here.

6. * Named contact.

The named contact is the guarantor for the accuracy of the information in the register record. This may be any member of the review team.

Rodrigo A. Giacaman

Email salutation (e.g. "Dr Smith" or "Joanne") for correspondence:

Professor Giacaman

7. * Named contact email.

Give the electronic email address of the named contact.

giacaman@utalca.cl

8. Named contact address

Give the full institutional/organisational postal address for the named contact.

1 Poniente 1141, Talca, Chile

9. Named contact phone number.

Give the telephone number for the named contact, including international dialling code.

+56976991129

10. * Organisational affiliation of the review.

Full title of the organisational affiliations for this review and website address if available. This field may be completed as 'None' if the review is not affiliated to any organisation.

University of Talca

Organisation web address:

www.utalca.cl

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11. * Review team members and their organisational affiliations.

Give the personal details and the organisational affiliations of each member of the review team. Affiliation refers to groups or organisations to which review team members belong. **NOTE: email and country now MUST be entered for each person, unless you are amending a published record.**

Professor Rodrigo Giacaman. University of Talca

Miss Lidia Contreras. University of Talca

Miss Camila Cid. University of Talca

Dr Karla Gambetta-Tessini. University of Talca

12. * Funding sources/sponsors.

Details of the individuals, organizations, groups, companies or other legal entities who have funded or sponsored the review.

None

Grant number(s)

State the funder, grant or award number and the date of award

None

13. * Conflicts of interest.

List actual or perceived conflicts of interest (financial or academic).

None

14. Collaborators.

Give the name and affiliation of any individuals or organisations who are working on the review but who are not listed as review team members. **NOTE: email and country must be completed for each person, unless you are amending a published record.**

15. * Review question.

State the review question(s) clearly and precisely. It may be appropriate to break very broad questions down into a series of related more specific questions. Questions may be framed or refined using PI(E)COS or similar where relevant.

Are there diagnostic methods for root caries lesions that have been correctly validated in the literature for clinical use?

16. * Searches.

State the sources that will be searched (e.g. Medline). Give the search dates, and any restrictions (e.g. language or publication date). Do NOT enter the full search strategy (it may be provided as a link or attachment below.)

A comprehensive search will be conducted from September 14th to November 20th through PubMed, Web of Science, and Scopus. No restriction of language or year of publication will be applied.

17. URL to search strategy.

Upload a file with your search strategy, or an example of a search strategy for a specific database, (including the keywords) in pdf or word format. In doing so you are consenting to the file being made publicly accessible. Or provide a URL or link to the strategy. Do NOT provide links to your search **results**.

https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/PROSPEROFILES/221968_STRATEGY_20201120.pdf

Alternatively, upload your search strategy to CRD in pdf format. Please note that by doing so you are consenting to the file being made publicly accessible.

Do not make this file publicly available until the review is complete

18. * Condition or domain being studied.

Give a short description of the disease, condition or healthcare domain being studied in your systematic review.

Root caries is an increasingly highly prevalent oral health problem among older persons. Higher longevity and tooth retention, better health care access, and more widely distributed preventive measures will mean higher root caries prevalence. Currently, no homogeneous diagnostic and assessment methods for root caries are available. Likewise, reporting on this condition is highly variable among studies, which precludes comparisons. The purpose of this review is to explore those methods with more scientific support, more broadly used in the clinic, and also which ones have reported higher accuracy. Assessment of conventional and no conventional root caries diagnosis methods available in the literature results relevant for researchers and clinicians.

19. * Participants/population.

Specify the participants or populations being studied in the review. The preferred format includes details of both inclusion and exclusion criteria.

This review will be conducted based on the research question according to the PICO question, where In vivo, Studies that do not study caries or do not extract teeth to allow caries assessment will be excluded (RE) where the reproducibility, specificity or sensitivity of the diagnostic method used is not reported and those reporting on coronal caries lesions will be excluded. Studies that combined the outcomes for coronal and root caries, will be excluded. Only root caries values, independently registered, will be included.

20. * Intervention(s), exposure(s).

Give full and clear descriptions or definitions of the interventions or the exposures to be reviewed. The preferred format includes details of both inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Intervention (I): Teeth with root caries lesions assessed by any diagnostic method.

21. * Comparator(s)/control.

Where relevant, give details of the alternatives against which the intervention/exposure will be compared (e.g. another intervention or a non-exposed control group). The preferred format includes details of both inclusion and exclusion criteria.

The comparisons will be made against the gold standard (histology) where possible. Otherwise, comparisons will be carried out between the examiners to calculate the reproducibility of the diagnostic method.

22. * Types of study to be included.

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Give details of the study designs (e.g. RCT) that are eligible for inclusion in the review. The preferred format includes both inclusion and exclusion criteria. If there are no restrictions on the types of study, this should be stated.

No restriction on study design. All in vivo, in situ or in vitro studies that assess diagnostic methods to detect root caries lesions will be eligible for inclusion, published in any language.

23. Context.

Give summary details of the setting or other relevant characteristics, which help define the inclusion or exclusion criteria.

24. * Main outcome(s).

Give the pre-specified main (most important) outcomes of the review, including details of how the outcome is defined and measured and when these measurements are made, if these are part of the review inclusion criteria.

~~Specify the primary and secondary~~ following outcomes:

-Reproducibility intra and inter-examiner

* Measures of effect

Please specify the effect measure(s) for your main outcome(s) e.g. relative risks, odds ratios, risk difference, and/or 'number needed to treat'.

~~Reproducibility intra and inter-examiner~~

25. * Additional outcome(s).

List the pre-specified additional outcomes of the review, with a similar level of detail to that required for main outcomes. Where there are no additional outcomes please state 'None' or 'Not applicable' as appropriate to the review

Diagnostic Accuracy

* Measures of effect

Please specify the effect measure(s) for your additional outcome(s) e.g. relative risks, odds ratios, risk difference, and/or 'number needed to treat'.

Accuracy is expressed as a percentage.

26. * Data extraction (selection and coding).

Describe how studies will be selected for inclusion. State what data will be extracted or obtained. State how this will be done and recorded.

Studies will be screened by title and abstract by 2 trained and calibrated independent researchers. Study selection will be carried out according to the PICO question previously defined. Once selected, the full text will be read and selected again against the PICO question and the inclusion and exclusion criteria. In vitro, In situ, and in vivo studies will be included. Study selection, data extraction will be done independently and in duplicate. When possible, data will be summarized and a meta-analysis will be conducted.

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27. * Risk of bias (quality) assessment.

State which characteristics of the studies will be assessed and/or any formal risk of bias/quality assessment tools that will be used.

Risk of bias will be determined using a combined strategy using modified tools; Rob 2, TorxTool and Maske.

The evaluation will be done independently and in duplicate. Quality assessment will be conducted using the Strobe checklist.

28. * Strategy for data synthesis.

Describe the methods you plan to use to synthesise data. This **must not be generic text** but should be **specific to your review** and describe how the proposed approach will be applied to your data. If meta-analysis is planned, describe the models to be used, methods to explore statistical heterogeneity, and software package to be used.

A descriptive summary analysis will be done following systematic review guidelines, in which the information from the included studies (Review Manager) will be used to meta-analyze homogeneous variables, if possible.

29. * Analysis of subgroups or subsets.

State any planned investigation of 'subgroups'. Be clear and specific about which type of study or participant will be included in each group or covariate investigated. State the planned analytic approach.

N/A

30. * Type and method of review.

Select the type of review, review method and health area from the lists below.

Type of review

Cost effectiveness

No

Diagnostic

Yes

Epidemiologic

Yes

Individual patient data (IPD) meta-analysis

No

Intervention

No

Meta-analysis

No

Methodology

No

Narrative synthesis

No

Network meta-analysis

No

Pre-clinical

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No

Prevention

No

Prognostic

No

Prospective meta-analysis (PMA)

No

Review of reviews

No

Service delivery

No

Synthesis of qualitative studies

No

Systematic review

Yes

Other

No

Health area of the review

Alcohol/substance misuse/abuse

No

Blood and immune system

No

Cancer

No

Cardiovascular

No

Care of the elderly

No

Child health

No

Complementary therapies

No

COVID-19

No

Crime and justice

No

Dental

Yes

Digestive system

No

Ear, nose and throat

No

Education

No

Endocrine and metabolic disorders

No

Eye disorders

No

General interest

No

Genetics

No

Health inequalities/health equity

No

Infections and infestations

No

International development

No

Mental health and behavioural conditions

No

Musculoskeletal

No

Neurological

No

Nursing

No

Obstetrics and gynaecology

No

Oral health

Yes

Palliative care

No

Perioperative care

No

Physiotherapy

No

Pregnancy and childbirth

No

Public health (including social determinants of health)

No

Rehabilitation

No

Respiratory disorders

No

Service delivery

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No

Skin disorders

No

Social care

No

Surgery

No

Tropical Medicine

No

Urological

No

Wounds, injuries and accidents

No

Violence and abuse

No

31. Language.

Select each language individually to add it to the list below, use the bin icon to remove any added in error.

English

There is an English language summary.

32. * Country.

Select the country in which the review is being carried out. For multi-national collaborations select all the countries involved.

Chile

33. Other registration details.

Name any other organisation where the systematic review title or protocol is registered (e.g. Campbell, or The Joanna Briggs Institute) together with any unique identification number assigned by them. If extracted data will be stored and made available through a repository such as the Systematic Review Data Repository (SRDR), details and a link should be included here. If none, leave blank.

34. Reference and/or URL for published protocol.

If the protocol for this review is published provide details (authors, title and journal details, preferably in Vancouver format)

Add web link to the published protocol.

Or, upload your published protocol here in pdf format. Note that the upload will be publicly accessible.

Yes I give permission for this file to be made publicly available

Please note that the information required in the PROSPERO registration form must be completed in full even if access to a protocol is given.

35. Dissemination plans.

Do you intend to publish the review on completion?

Yes

Give brief details of plans for communicating review findings.?

The final report will be published in an international dental journal. These results may be helpful in presenting validated tools for root caries assessment to clinicians and also provide recommendations to clinical and epidemiological researchers on diagnostic methods to facilitate data comparison from the different studies in the field.

36. Keywords.

Give words or phrases that best describe the review. Separate keywords with a semicolon or new line. Keywords help PROSPERO users find your review (keywords do not appear in the public record but are included in searches). Be as specific and precise as possible. Avoid acronyms and abbreviations unless these are in wide use.

Root caries, Diagnosis, Reproducibility, Accuracy, Specificity, Sensitivity.

37. Details of any existing review of the same topic by the same authors.

If you are registering an update of an existing review give details of the earlier versions and include a full bibliographic reference, if available.

N/A

38. * Current review status.

Update review status when the review is completed and when it is published. New registrations must be ongoing so this field is not editable for initial submission.

Please provide anticipated publication date

Review_Ongoing

39. Any additional information.

Provide any other information relevant to the registration of this review.

40. Details of final report/publication(s) or preprints if available.

Leave empty until publication details are available OR you have a link to a preprint (NOTE: this field is not editable for initial submission). List authors, title and journal details preferably in Vancouver format.

Give the link to the published review or preprint.